

Movement and Transformation of Anhydrous Ammonia in Field Soil

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Movement of ammonia under the experimental condition was found to be within 3.7 cm radius from the line of injection and this was associated with rise of pH of the soil. After 22 days of application, this pH however approached its original value. Transformation of applied NH_3 to NO_3^- started from the periphery of the horizontal cylindrically shaped ammonia retention zone and it approached the point of injection. Appreciable nitrification started only after 7 days of ammonia application. Initial slow nitrification suggests preplanting application of anhydrous ammonia in dry field and then incorporation of irrigation water within 7 days without appreciable loss of added nitrogen through leaching of nitrate.

THE use of anhydrous ammonia (82.2% N) as a source of nitrogen to soil application and study of its behaviour started long back in the west¹ but no systematic work has been done in eastern countries. Due to its high alkaline nature unlike any conventional solid nitrogenous fertilizer anhydrous ammonia creates an alkaline zone in the soil at the immediate vicinity of its point of application. The rise in pH as well as accumulation of NH_3 at this particular zone affect the soil nitrifying organisms resulting in some change in the nitrification rate in anhydrous ammonia treated soil as compared to soils treated with conventional nitrogenous fertilizers². Nitrification is most favourable in neutral to slightly alkaline soil³ i.e. between pH 7 to 8. The high pH and the high concentration of ammonia and ammonium resulting on the application of anhydrous ammonia are toxic to soil-microbes and cause partially sterilised condition at the maximum retention zone. Accordingly, nitrification starts around the periphery of the horizontal cylindrically shaped zone of ammonia retention and then proceeds towards the point of injection⁴.

The present study was undertaken with a view to understand the distribution pattern of applied anhydrous ammonia as well as its nitrification rate in field soil at Rice Production Training Institute, Hindustan Fertilizer Corporation, Durgapur, West Bengal in order to find out the possibility of use of anhydrous ammonia as a fertilizer for upland row crop as well as lowland paddy cultivation under Indian soil climatic conditions.

Materials and Methods :

The land of the experimental site was first well prepared for the application of anhydrous ammonia. Anhydrous ammonia was applied by an applicator, designed and fabricated by Markstig, Denmark, at a depth of 11.5 cm. The dose was fixed by a nitro-

leter fitted at the top of the applicator. The applicator was pulled by a tractor. During application, ammonia was pushed through the sharp spring loaded nozzles into the soil and the lines of injection were covered with soil very quickly by trailer harrow.

Several lines of injection were marked with pegs above the soil. Periodical estimations of pH, ammoniacal, nitrite and nitrate-nitrogen were done on samples drawn from different depths as well as from different horizontal distances from the line of injection upto 98 days after application. The soil samples were collected by cutting pits and exposing vertical surface at an angle of 90° with the line of injection. The exact depth and line of injection was found out by using filterpaper soaked with Nessler's solution. Soil samples were collected from different distances vertically (both upward and downward) and laterally from the point of injection on the cut perpendicular to the line of injection, by stainless steel soil sampler of 2.5 cm diameter. Samples were taken in weighed conical flasks with 50ml extractant, immediately after sampling in the field, and the weight of soil sample was determined from difference in weight. Moisture percentage was determined at different depths separately. pH was measured with an Elico pH meter model L 1-10 with soil water ratio 1 : 2. Ammonical and nitrite nitrogen were extracted with 2M KCl solution⁵. Nitrate nitrogen was extracted with CuSO_4 , Ag_2SO_4 extractant from separate soil samples⁶. $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ was estimated colorimetrically by Nessler's method, $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$ by α -naphthylamine sulphanic acid method and $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ by phenyl disulphonic acid method. Colour intensities were measured by photo electric colorimeter at wave lengths 420 m μ , 540 m μ and 420 m μ , for $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$, $\text{NO}_2\text{-N}$ and $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$, respectively. Soil temperature at a depth of 11.5 cm was also recorded.

The soil of the experimental site is loamy. Its general characteristics is given in Table 1. Vertical

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TABLE 1—GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SOIL

	Percentage (oven dry basis)
Sand	78.8
Silt	3.2
Clay	18.2
Organic C	0.55
Total N	0.056
Available N	0.015
Available K (ppm)	63.7
Cation exchange capacity (me/100 gm)	11.4
Conductivity (m mhos/cm ²)	0.098
pH	5.1

changes of pH, NH₄⁺-N and NO₃⁻-N are shown in Figs. 1, 2 and 3 respectively. Figs. 1A, 2A and 3A show the lateral changes of pH, NH₄⁺-N and NO₃⁻-N respectively. Recorded soil temperature at the injection depth 11.5 cm varied from 24° to 17° during the period under study. Soil moisture at 11.5 cm depth varied from 8-12%.

Results and Discussion

Changes of soil pH : The immediate effect of anhydrous ammonia application was rise of pH at the centre and immediate vicinity of the line of injection. Just at the line of injection, pH increased upto 8.1 after 2 days after 2 days and movement of ammonia was upto 3.8 cm both vertically and laterally. From Figs. 1 and 1A it is clear that after 22 days, pH of the soil returned more or less to its original value.

Fig. 1. pH Changes in soil (vertical).
 — before application
 ●—● 2 days after application
 ○—○ 7 " " "
 △—△ 22 " " "
 - - - - 98 " " "

Fig. 1A. pH Changes in soil (lateral).
 — before application
 ●—● 2 days after application
 ○—○ 7 " " "
 △—△ 22 " " "
 - - - - 98 " " "

After 98 days pH decreased even below the original pH, depthwise upto 20.0 cm. From Fig. 1A it is evident that lowering of pH was maximum after 22 days. After 98 days pH was relatively higher at all distances from the line of injection laterally. This may be due to leaching of nitrate to higher depths due to rainfall. Upto 22 days there was no rainfall while between 22 days and 98 days intermittent precipitation took place. From the pH curves it is revealed that under the experimental condition movement of applied anhydrous ammonia has not been more than 4 cm from the line of injection, both vertically and horizontally.

Changes of ammoniacal nitrogen : Changes of ammoniacal nitrogen concentration due to anhydrous ammonia application have been shown in Fig. 2 and 2A. Localized accumulation of applied NH₃ within 4 cm radius from the line of injection was observed. After 2 days of application the highest concentration of NH₃ at the line of injection was 1068 ppm while at 2.5 cm distance it varied from 433 to 451 ppm both laterally and vertically. Exchangable ammonia was appreciably high on the line of injection throughout the period under study though it decreased with time. Presence of NH₄⁺-N at greater depths was not observed except after 98 days (Fig. 2) when appreciable accumulation of ammonia (197 ppm) was recorded at 22.5-25.0 cm depth. This might be due to leaching of nitrate from above due to rainfall and subsequent reduction to ammoniacal form.

Fig. 2. Vertical movement of ammonium nitrogen.

— before application
 ●—● 2 days after application
 ○—○ 7 " " "
 △—△ 22 " " "
 - - - 98 " " "

Changes of nitrate-nitrogen : In Figs. 3 and 3A vertical and lateral distribution of nitrate nitrogen

Fig. 3. Changes in nitrate nitrogen concentration (vertical).

— before application
 ●—● 2 days after application
 ○—○ 7 " " "
 △—△ 22 " " "
 - - - 98 " " "

Fig. 2A. Lateral movement of ammonium nitrogen.

— before application
 ●—● 2 days after application
 ○—○ 7 " " "
 △—△ 22 " " "
 - - - 98 " " "

Fig. 3A. Lateral movement of nitrate nitrogen.

— before application
 ●—● 2 days after application
 ○—○ 7 " " "
 △—△ 22 " " "
 - - - 98 " " "

Changes of nitrite-nitrogen : Estimation of nitrite nitrogen was made depthwise as well as laterally. No accumulation of nitrite was observed at any point. Even at the line of injection accumulation of nitrite was very little or no nitrite was recorded.

has been shown. At 2 days and 7 days after application, rate of nitrification was noticeably less in comparison to that after 22 days. After 2 days and 7 days intervals the rates of nitrification were approximately 1% and 2.5% respectively. Moreover, the rate was higher at the periphery of the horizontal cylindrically shaped anhydrous ammonia retention zone. This suggests a partial sterilization of the soil by anhydrous ammonia application^{2,7}. Nitrification was appreciable after 22 days both laterally and vertically. Fig. 3A shows lateral movement of nitrate-nitrogen after 22 days upto 12.5 to 15 cm distance from the line of injection with gradual decrease. This might be due to diffusion of nitrate through soil solution. Fig. 3 shows that vertical distribution of nitrate was not appreciable at greater depths beyond 18 cm. This is because of instability of nitrate at higher moisture condition (where partial water logging leads to reduction). This is supported by higher pH and moisture percentage at greater depths.

From the movement and transformation study of anhydrous ammonia in field soil the following conclusion could be drawn.

- A. Movement of ammonia in soil under the experimental condition was within 3.7 cm radius from the line of injection and this was associated with a rise of pH. The pH, however, approached its original value after 22 days of application of anhydrous ammonia.
- B. Transformation of added NH_3 to nitrate started from the periphery of the horizontal cylindrically shaped ammonia retention zone and it moved towards the point of injection. This might be, as stated earlier, due to partial sterilization of soil microbes by free ammonia⁴.
- C. Estimation of nitrite nitrogen revealed no nitrite accumulation at the line of injection unlike observations reported by other workers⁸⁻¹⁰.
- D. Nitrification was negligible upto 7 days from the date of ammonia application and thereafter appreciable nitrification started.

The above observations are interesting and promising for upland row crop and water logged paddy

cultivation. Restricted movement of ammonia suggests a possibility of using anhydrous ammonia as side dresser without appreciable root damage to standing crop or germination of sown seed. Secondly, the initially slow nitrification of added NH_3 suggests a way out for preplanting application of anhydrous ammonia in dry field and subsequent incorporation of water for irrigation within 7 days without appreciable loss of added nitrogen through leaching of nitrate. Thereafter the nitrification is fairly rapid so as to support the initial growth of the tender plants as well as the standing crop. Hence the possibility of the use of anhydrous ammonia as a fertilizer seems to be promising.

Some doubts from time to time that exist about proper use of anhydrous ammonia are due to probable high volatilisation loss under high atmospheric temperature prevailing in India and small land holding coupled with poor level of farm mechanisation. But these are not fully convincing. While volatilisation loss can be checked considerably by adopting proper agronomic practices and manipulating the application technique, small ammonia applicators can easily be operated on Custom Hire-Service in agriculturally developed areas of Punjab, Haryana, Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, Tamilnadu, Andhra Pradesh and West Bengal where tractor drawn equipments are already in use.

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